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GREEN LOGISTICS: ANOTHER ENGINEERING IS POSSIBLE

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One of the goals of an engineer is to solve problems, and a second one is to reduce costs. This is usually related to real life situations and daily life.

A team made of companies from different European countries started working with some universities in LOG-IN-GREEN project, for training green logistics managers to avoid the environmental effects of logistics. This project's aim is to improve green logistics skills in young workers. Once trained, young workers will become green logistics trainers, and this will help to the employability of young people. Logistics education and awareness require good knowledge of geography and also foreign languages and human relations skills as well as digital competences. There are standard trainings that are being used in the sector.

For doing this, we have discussed about some methodologies that will help students to acquire the competencies to become green logistics managers. Universities and companies can find together the way to teach young people. This workshop will deal with different methodologies that are proposed for engineers to train logistics leaders and future trainers.

The current situation in some European cities is that young people with migrant backgrounds, immigrants and refugees, young people at risk of marginalisation, or young people with fewer opportunities (including NEETs, not in education, employment or training) apply for a job and want to be integrated into the labour market.

Motivation and the use of technology are the key points to reach this target group. Youngsters like to be connected all day and they usually love playing games.

Keeping this in mind, we propose a practical session to teach and learn about different engineering topics. We will present a real scenario where participants will develop their engineering, social and team work skills to achieve the best results.

The use of games (game-based learning), design thinking, online learning, learning using mobile devices, or mental or conceptual maps, are some methodologies and tools that are currently being used in several educational contexts. The mobile phone

(usually forbidden for teaching and learning) plays a key role in the process of training. Participants in this workshop will be encouraged to use their mobile phones and also to participate in a game and thereby test the possibilities of these methodologies. Escape rooms or Breakout EDU are becoming activities to motivate students, to make them work in teams, and to address real situations that must be solved finding clues and applying previously acquired knowledge.

We propose a session with speakers from different engineering areas with the common goal of engaging and training young people. The use of games or mobile devices in education of people over 15 is not very widespread. It is not common to use games for teaching Linear Algebra, Calculus, Mechanics, Logistics, Thermotechnics, or any other subject. Students must learn theoretical topics and how to solve several problems in a “classical” way, although these problems could be real-life problems. During recent years we are trying to make students apply what they learn while they try to solve engineering and scientific problems.

The participation in this session may provide ideas and tools for supporting trainers and trainees in the final goal of reaching the needs of young people. Furthermore, the development of a new approach is being demanded by engineers to motivate young workers, and also for youngsters to be motivated with learning.

We propose to play Angry Birds and not solve an interpolation problem, to find the key to open a padlocked box instead of listing ecolabels of a product, or decrypt an encrypted message to get the uses of ecological footprint. Young people would rather solve a puzzle, than memorize a list of polluting gases or solve an optimization problem.

During some undergraduate and master degrees we have implemented game-based learning with physics and maths topics. These activities engage students in learning contents and acquiring engineering competencies and skills. Gamers learn by doing and by experimenting, and they participate as part of a team. Their motivation is guaranteed as they like play games to win.